

Search for Possible New Anthelmintic Compounds : Part V Synthesis of Phenolic-salts of Piperazine and Piperazino- carbonyl-methyl-Dithiocarbamic acid esters

S. S. TIWARI and (MISS) SUMAN BALA MISRA

Chemistry Department, Lucknow University, Lucknow

Manuscript received 25 October 1975; accepted 19 February 1976

Ten phenolic salts of piperazine and eleven N_4 -aryl- N_1 -piperazino-carbonylmethyl-dithiocarbamic acid-esters of piperazines and other secondary amines have been synthesized. A few compounds of this series were subjected for their anthelmintic and antiamebic properties.

THE phenolic salts of piperazine have been reported to exhibit marked anthelmintic activity¹. In addition some piperazine salts of halogen substituted phenol² and Fenasal piperazine salts³ have been shown to be more active and potent. The greatest advantage of these salts is that they are active at non-toxic level. Further, ester of dithiocarbamic acids have been established as the broad spectrum anthelmintics for the treatment of liver fluke⁴⁻⁶ *Opisthorchis* infections.

Authors, therefore, thought it worthwhile to extend the scope and validity of these observations to piperazine-1,4-bis-[*o*-(aminocarbonyl)-phenolates] and N_4 -aryl- N_1 -piperazino-carbonyl-methyl-dithiocarbamic acid esters of piperazine and other secondary amines.

Experimental

All the melting points were determined in open capillaries in H_2SO_4 melting point bath and are uncorrected.

(1) Piperazine-1,4-bis-[*o*-(aminocarbonyl)-phenolates] :

A mixture of 2-aminocarbonyl phenol⁷ (0.02 mole) and piperazine hexahydrate (0.01 mole) was refluxed in absolute ethanol on a steam bath for a period of 6 hr under anhydrous conditions. The solid obtained after concentration of the solvent, was recrystallised from benzene-petroleum ether (40°-60°). The melting points and analytical data of these compounds are reported in Table I.

TABLE I

Sl. no.	R	M.P. °C	Yield %	Molecular formula	Analysis Nitrogen%	
					Calcd.	Found
*1.	Anilino	130	70	$C_{30}H_{32}N_4O_4$	10.93	10.84
2.	<i>o</i> -Toluidino	141	65	$C_{32}H_{36}N_4O_4$	10.37	10.18
3.	<i>p</i> -Toluidino	154	75	$C_{32}H_{36}N_4O_4$	10.37	10.02
4.	<i>o</i> -Anisidino	163	60	$C_{32}H_{36}N_4O_6$	9.79	9.54
5.	<i>p</i> -Anisidino	153	68	$C_{32}H_{36}N_4O_6$	9.79	9.28
*6.	α -Naphthylamino	165	75	$C_{38}H_{36}N_4O_4$	9.15	8.98
7.	Diphenyl amino	189	80	$C_{42}H_{40}N_4O_4$	8.43	8.12
8.	2-Aminopyridino	180	70	$C_{28}H_{30}N_6O_4$	16.34	15.82
9.	Phenothiazino	100	68	$C_{42}H_{36}N_4O_4S_2$	7.73	7.42
10.	Morpholino	110	75	$C_{26}H_{36}N_4O_6$	11.20	10.88

(2) *Piperazine-1,4-bis-(N₄-aryl-N₁-piperazino-carbonyl methyl dithiocarbamic acid esters)* :

To a solution of N₄-aryl-N₁-chloro acetyl piperazine (0.02 mole)⁸ in dry acetone, piperazine 1,4-bis-(dithio-sodium carbamate)⁹ (0.01 mole) was added, the resultant solution was stirred for 1/2 hr and then poured over crushed ice and was allowed to stand for 1 hr at room temperature. The solid which separated out, was washed several times with water and recrystallised from alcohol. These compounds were characterized with their sharp melting points and elemental analyses (Table 2).

(3) *N₄-Aryl-N₁-piperazino-carbonyl methyl dithiocarbamic acid esters of secondary amines* :

An equimolar mixture of N₄-aryl-N₁-chloro acetyl piperazine⁸ and dithio sodium carbamate⁹ of appropriate secondary amine in dry acetone was refluxed for 24 hr. on a water bath under anhydrous conditions. After the reaction was complete the reaction mixture was filtered to remove inorganic salts and the solvent was distilled off under reduced pressure. The resulting crude solid was recrystallised from ethyl alcohol. These crystals were very well characterized with their sharp melting points and elemental data. (Table 3).

TABLE 2

Sl. no.	R'	M.P. °C	Yield %	Molecular formula	Analysis Nitrogen %	
					Calcd.	Found
1.	<i>m</i> -Tolyl	94	80	C ₅₂ H ₄₂ N ₆ O ₂ S ₄	12.53	12.12
*2.	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	145	85	C ₃₀ H ₃₆ N ₆ O ₂ S ₄ Cl ₂	11.74	11.42

TABLE 3

Sl. no.	R'	R	M.P. °C	Yield %	Molecular formula	Analysis nitrogen %	
						Calcd.	Found
1.	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	Morpholino	101	70	C ₁₇ H ₂₂ N ₃ O ₂ S ₂ Cl	10.52	10.14
2.	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	Dimethylamine	135	75	C ₁₈ H ₂₀ N ₃ OS ₂ Cl	11.76	11.22
3.	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	Piperidino	114	74	C ₁₈ H ₂₄ N ₃ OS ₂ Cl	10.57	9.98
4.	<i>m</i> -Tolyl	Morpholino	75	72	C ₁₆ H ₂₆ N ₃ O ₂ S ₂	11.08	10.74
5.	<i>m</i> -Tolyl	Dimethylamino	143	75	C ₁₆ H ₂₃ N ₃ OS ₂	12.46	12.12
6.	<i>m</i> -Tolyl	Piperidino	72	80	C ₁₆ H ₂₇ N ₃ OS ₂	11.14	10.94
*7.	<i>o</i> -Tolyl	Morpholino	96	75	C ₁₆ H ₂₆ N ₃ O ₂ S ₂	11.08	10.78
8.	<i>o</i> -Tolyl	Dimethylamino	91	78	C ₁₆ H ₂₃ N ₃ OS ₂	12.46	12.02
*9.	<i>o</i> -Tolyl	Piperidino	85	80	C ₁₆ H ₂₇ N ₃ OS ₂	11.14	10.76

Pharmacology :

Five compounds (having asterisk mark in the Tables 1, 2 and 3) were screened against *Nippostrongylus brasiliensis* at a dose level of 250 mg/kg (*in vivo*). However, none of compounds was found to show any significant anthelmintic activity.

Three compounds number 1, 2 and 5 (Table 3) were screened for antiamoebic activity by technique of Das¹⁰ and were found to possess significant activity at 62 µg/ml (1 : 16000 dilution) against *Entamoeba histolytica*.

Acknowledgement

Thanks are due to Dr. N. Nand, Director, Central Drug Research Institute, Lucknow for elemental and pharmacological data reported herein. The authors are also grateful to C.S.I.R. for the award of a junior research fellowship to one of them (SBM).

References

1. R. RICHARD, B. GABREILLE, T. M. CHAU and C. RAYMOND, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1973, **16**, 725.
2. W. S. FRANKLIN and F. E. EDWARD, *J. Med. Pharm. Chem.*, 1962, **5**, 642.
3. A. G. KHALILOV, *Med. Parazitol. Parazit*, 1972, **41**, 419.
4. M. SCHORR, W. DUERCKHEIMER and D. DUEWEL, Ger offen 1,812,142, 1970. *Chem. Abs.*, 1970, **73**, 56094h.
5. M. SCHORR, W. DUERCKHEIMER, L. BEHRENDT and D. DUEWEL, Ger.offen, 1,947,746, 1971. *Chem. Abs.*, 1971, **75**, 5531g.
6. FARBERWERKE HOECHST A-G, Fr. Demande 2,015,026, 1970. *Chem. Abs.*, 1971, **75**, 5534k.
7. C. F. H. ALLEN and J. A. VAN ALLEN, *Org. Synth.*, 1946, **26**, 92.
8. S. HAYAO, H. J. HAVERA, W. G. STRYCKER and T. J. LEIPZIG, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1967, **10**, 400.
9. T. MITSUO, T. YOSHIMASO, K. YOSHITOSHI, T. YASUO, T. YOICHI and Y. YOKO, *Kumamoto. Pharm. Bull.*, 1962, **5**, 24.
10. S. R. DAS, *Current Sci.*, 1975, **44**, 463.